

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

DELIVERABLE TITLE

D2.1 INTEGER-Inter-ecosystem hands-on visits plan

Call and Topic: HORIZON-EIE-2022-CONNECT-01-02

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The study visits will be an important step for the project. The project consortium will learn about the regional innovation ecosystems and get personal contact with regional stakeholders. Furthermore, the study visits will be very important to promote the project in the regions.

The study visits will follow the principle of cross-sectoral collaboration. The Quadruple helix model will bring together stakeholders from different fields and will be a starting point for as well cooperation inside the regions as for interregional cooperation. Inter-regions study visits will put in contact key social and digital business innovators from the three regions.

The visits are important for the consortium, to define a common understanding of innovation and relevant stakeholder groups. But it is also important to see what different stakeholder groups define as innovative and what type of mechanisms are existing in the regions, that helps to improve innovation.

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aim

One of the main aims of INTEGER is the collaboration, the mutual learning and the exchange among regions from different cultural settings, backgrounds and styles of innovation. Being exposed to:

- a) diverse innovation ecosystems;
- b) different ways to address the gap between the different types of innovation (social-technology-business driven) and
- c) Distinct ways

The three planned regional study visits had several objectives:

1. Map, select, contact and invite a group of key stakeholders from the quadruple helix spectrum in order to team up with them for the project duration to accomplish the objectives and activities planned;
2. To learn from inspirational cases of social/business innovations already in place or in development in each of the regions;
3. To identify the main challenges of quadruple helix collaboration and co-creation mechanisms;
4. To start collecting ideas for the INTEGER 4H comprehensive model;
5. To start identifying Minimum Viable Products and Services that could be later worked on in later stages of the project (e.g. the col-laborathons) to test the bilateral collaborative approach from the social-driven innovation and the business innovation side; and
6. To begin building or reinforcing 4H committed and interested communities at three levels. Within the context of each of the regions, among the three regions and at EU level (preparing the ground for the constitution of the INTEGER EU Col-laboratory on Health and Wellbeing in September 2023).

In each of the three regions, key social and digital business innovators, who play a significant role and are vital actors in healthy living, active ageing policy and social exclusion areas were going to put in contact to exchange and co-think together on the above mentioned objectives.

The study visits were planned at the KoM for the following dates in each of the regions:

- Barcelona: 15 February 2023;
- Krakow/Malopolska region: 28 and 29 March 2023; and
- Hamburg; two days, 30 and 31 March 2023.

For cost and time effectiveness, the second and third study visits were planned in a combined way during the same week of March.

1.2 Catalan region Study Visit

Previously to the Catalan study visit in mid February we ran a preparation phase with a couple of information sessions in order to explain the Catalan key stakeholders from the quadruple helix the Integer project and invite them to participate in it.

First information and co-creating session was held **physically at the i2Cat Foundation offices on December 13th 2022** where we invited potential stakeholders that some of them were already participating at the Catalonia Col·laboratory since around one year before. Catalonia Col·laboratory is a local initiative promoted by the Catalanian Government and executed by i2Cat. The Health and Wellbeing Catalanian Collaboratory aims to create a local network around health and wellbeing and with the potential participation of 4 helix organisations in order to identify common interests for collaboration around jointly identified challenges with the digital tools as a lever. For this first session we invited around 120 people. 54 people filled the registration form and 46 people finally attended the session in person! It was a 90% success rate between the registered people and the attendances.

The session took 3h long and it was based on three main parts. The first one was dedicated to making an introduction and explanation of the EIC call expected outcomes and the INTEGER's aims. For the second part we created different subject tables and through co-creation methods we tried to identify the needs and know-how from the different interested organisations. Finally, the third part of the event was focused on asking the attendees to sign the *Letter of Intent (LOI) or Expression of Interest* ([here](#)) that we previously created regarding the INTEGER project in order to register stakeholders' interest and commitment for further participation.

Agenda of the information session held at i2Cat Foundation on Dec 13th 2022.

10:00 Welcome and self-introductions from the different participants (Leads: R Nualart).

10:15 The Catalan Health and Welfare Collaboratory (Leads: T Caro)

10:18 Catalanian Collaboratory, DST area and i2Cat Foundation. (Leads: A Serra)

10:30 INTEGER 4H. What is it? How does it arise? How do you connect with Catalanian Collaboratory? The European Agenda -Musketters video + EU Horizon Image, EU dilemma- 10' FAQs (Leads: T Caro)

10:55 Participatory dynamics 4H. Introduction (Leads: T Caro)

11:00 Inspiring cases. 2' Elevator pitch for each table/group. (Leads: R. Nualart)

11:15 4H Co-creation. The 5 teams in different tables/subjects look for a main idea based on some questions and a theme. (Leads: one 2Cat member for each subject table)

- What health and welfare systems/what lifestyles/what socio-economic impacts do these cases pursue?

- Which minimally viable products or services can have a public or private nature and pursue socio-economic benefits for society (food, exercise, well-being, ...)?

12:00 Each team presents its main idea, the headline, what do we keep from the discussion? Something new and shocking! (3'x5) Leads: (R. Nualart)

12:15 LOI or Expression of Interest. Collab Health and Welfare constitution agreement and membership (Leads: T Caro)

12:25 Next steps (Leads: T Caro)

12:30 Closing and networking (Leads: I2Cat members)

Second information session was held **online on February 2nd 2023** for the people that could not attend the previous information physical session on Dec 13th.

The session took just one hour long and was mainly focused on explaining about the Integer project as well as trying to involve more organisations through the LOI. We also took advantage to briefly introduce the digital Theglocal.Network platform that we were just building up for INTEGER 4H.

For this second information session we invited a total of 74 people and finally 39 people attended the session. Due the session was held online, it was not necessary to previously fill a registration form

Agenda of the INTEGER 4H online information session on Feb 2nd 2023.

13:00 Welcome and self-introductions from the different participants (R. Nualart)

13:10 The Health & Welfare Catalonia Collaboratory (R. Nualart)

13:12 Catalanian Collaboratory, DST area and i2Cat Foundation. (A. Serra)

13:20 INTEGER 4H. What is it? How does it arise? How do you connect with Catalonia Collaboratory? The European agenda -video musketeers + EU Horizon image, EU dilemma.- 5' FAQs (T. Caro)

13:40 LOI or Expression of Interest. Collab Health and Welfare constitution agreement and membership (T. Caro)

13:45 Theglocal.network (X. Albalà)

13:55 Closing and thanks (R Nualart)

Finally a total of 85 people from different 4 helix organisations attended both information sessions and between both information sessions we got a total of 49 signatures of the Expression of interest document. 27 in paper format and 22 in digital format.

Within the first physical session of the preparation phase on Dec 13th, as we explained. We run a co-creation session with all the participants splitted on different tables. Each table was focused on a specific subject with one inspiring case in order to facilitate the later questions and discussion.

The subjects and inspiring cases for each one of the tables/groups were:

01. **Ageing** - M. Inzitari. Pere Virgili Institute. BALL
02. **Pollution and health** - M. Rofin. Bax & Company. Healthy Cities Generator
03. **Nutrition** - M. Martorell. i2Cat. Green Schools
04. **Social and labour inclusion** - (1) T. Codina. iSocial. Nidus. (2) C. Sopenya. Fundación Viver de Bell-lloc. Labour Inclusion and Training.
05. **Physical exercise** - E. Polo. CitiLab. ActivaLab.

The proposed questions in order to create a debate with the participants' own experience and know-how and with the background inspirational cases were:

01. What health and welfare systems do they pursue in these cases?
02. What socio-economic impacts do they chase these cases?
03. What styles of life pursue these cases?
04. Which minimally viable products or services can have a public or private nature and pursue socio-economic benefits (food, exercise, well-being, ...)?

The final summary for each table was:

Mechanisms for Social and Business-Driven Innovations

Are there mechanisms with capacity or potential to merge Social-driven and business-driven innovations? Which are the perceived **opportunities and barriers**?

Integrating Business and Social Driven Innovation

Not really strong mechanisms have been built yet. Some basic collaboration methodology with digital tools and space. We identified common interests such different inspirational success cases:

- Working together for ageing at the **SeniorLab**
- **Cities Health Generator** (for urban planners) from Bax & Co.
- **FIT4food** from Allison Innovation Network. IrsiCaixa
- Social and digital impact Integration from **AEMA Foundation and Xarxa Punt TIC**
- Promoting wellbeing culture for orgs from **Biwel**.
- **Saluscoop**. Anonymized health data.
- Labour and social inclusion from **Bell-Iloc Foundation**
- **Green schools & paths** from Teia city council
- **Nidus** from iSocial, and app for homeless
- Exercise promotion from **ActivaLab**.
- Research for ageing from **BALL** (Barcelona Aging Living Lab)

How INTEGER could help?

How do you envisage INTEGER supporting your regional quadruple ecosystem to bring closer and quicker Minimum Viable Products or Services to the market and society?

1. **Identifying together proactive organizations** with the aim to collaborate for win win goals.
2. **Generating actions and activities** for the benefits of the different participants organizations.
3. **Helping to identify complementarities and common interests** between the Integer participants organizations, both at local or international level.
4. **Been focus on projects and actions** with a mid term benefit more than on activities definitions.
5. Spending the time for **real benefits and impacts**, social & private
6. **Helping to identify funding programs**, private or public.
7. Providing support and guidelines about **how to apply on public funding programs**.
8. Understanding how really **collaborate considering the four helix** different interests.
9. Understanding **how digital field could help** for a final success due the process itself or the final applied technology.
10. Visualizing the opportunities and organizations **further than my already mostly recognised surrounding**.
11. Visualizing new opportunities thanks **to know and discover complementary organizations** and their specific expertise and know how
12. With all the **local background, experience and knowledge** from the different regions partners.
13. Providing **a space to share and to be in contact**

Following the regions introductions, we run the first co-creation session with the following questions working by tables/groups trying to know the reasons and mechanisms for 4Helix collaborations and social driven and business-driven innovations as well as the opportunities and barriers.

We continued allowing 5 local stakeholders, one per table/subject, to explain within 5' their own inspirational success cases for a later discussion motivation and as different collaboration examples within the health & wellbeing field. The subjects or themes for each table were the same ones as the information session held on Dec 13th but with different inspirational cases except for one of the tables that repeated it but with a deep explanation of it. For this study visit the inspirational cases were:

- 01. Ageing.** L. Pallejà from Reus Ciutat Sàvia. Senior Lab.
- 02. Pollution.** M. Rofin from Bax & Company. Healthy Urban Generator
- 03. Nutrition.** R. Malagrida from IrsiCaixa. Allison Network.
- 04. Social/laboral inclusion.** I. Malick from AEMA Foundation. La Florida.
- 05. Physical exercise.** O. Aragay from Biwel

After a short and healthy break we ran the second co-creation session that, continuing on the tables/subjects and motivated for the inspirational cases, first of all was mainly focused on sharing know-how and experiences and later on INTEGER 4H win-win definitions and expectations as well as governance potential issues.

Finally we run a wrap up with the conclusions of each table before to explain the next steps and share a more relaxed closing networking.

Catalonian Study Visit Agenda held in Barcelona on Feb 15th 2023

Venue: Catalonia Public Health Department

Address: Salvany Building, **SALA POLIVALENT**, Roc Boronat, 81, 08005 Barcelona

15:00. **Institutional welcome.** T. Caro from i2Cat Foundation. Integer Coordinator. All attendees stand up one by one and quickly introduce themselves with name and organisation

- Catalonia Health Department. Public Health Responsible. A. Bocio
- Catalonia Col·laboratori Health & Wellbeing. i2Cat Foundation. R. Nualart
- Hamburg Government. K. Schnackenberg
- Krakowia Jagiellonian University. J. Perek - Bialas

15:30. **Co-creation Session 1.**

1. *Which are the main facts, figures and relevant initiatives (timeline, for instance) that point out to quadruple helix collaborations?*
2. *Are there mechanisms with capacity or potential to merge Social-driven and business-driven innovations? Which are the perceived opportunities and barriers?*

16:00. **Inspiring thematic case presentations.**

- Ageing. L. Pallejà from Reus Ciutat Sàvia. Senior Lab.
- Pollution. M. Rofin from Bax & Co. Healthy Urban Generator
- Nutrition. R. Malagrida from IrsiCaixa. Allison Network.
- Social/labour inclusion. I. Malick from AEMA Foundation. PTic La Florida.
- Physical exercise. O. Aragay from Biwel

16:30. **Networking Coffee Break!**

16:50. **Co-creation Session 2.**

Sharing experiences and cases worth sharing

1. *What needs do you have, usually?*
2. *What is your own specific and concrete added value or know how.*
3. *What kind of unique product or services do you have?*
4. *Identify potential or existing Minimum Viable Product and/or Services within the social innovation*

Expectations and win win definitions

1. *Indicate Governance and challenges for the 4 helix collaboration*
2. *How do you envisage INTEGER supporting your regional quadruple ecosystem to bring closer and quicker Minimum Viable Products or Services to the market and society?*

17:45. Wrap Up**17:55. Next steps & closing****18.00. Networking Coffee break for a future wellbeing!****18:30. End**

1.3 Malopolska region Study Visit

Two project partners representing Krakow Technology Park and the Jagiellonian University have been responsible for the organisation of the joint study visit to Krakow by the end of March 2023 according to the project timeline.

The aim of the study visit is to put in contact key social and digital business innovators who play a significant role and are vital actors in healthy living, active ageing policy and social exclusion areas in Krakow and Malopolska region. The study visit was planned for two days, 28 and 29 March 2023.

28 March 2023 VENUE: Jagiellonian University Address: Collegium Novum, 24 Gołębia Street, room no. 30	
9.30 - 9.45	Welcome and introduction to Malopolska 3H i 4H actors, challenges and ecosystem <i>Jolanta Perek-Białas, The Jagiellonian University</i> Małopolska ecosystem of startups and innovators as a drive for boosting social innovation <i>Monika Machowska, Kraków Technology Park</i>
9.45 - 10.15	Aging Policy in the City of Krakow <i>Jolanta Perek-Białas, The Jagiellonian University</i>
10.15 - 10.30	Innovation for social change - Jagiellonian University experience <i>Krystian Gurba, Centre for Technology Transfer CITTRU</i>
10.30 - 11.00	Social Innovation Incubator – from vision to action. Best practices <i>Katarzyna Ociepka-Miąsik, Regional Center for Social Policy</i>
	Coffee, Tea, Water - during a meeting will be served
11.00 - 11.45	Moderated discussion on current status and key challenges <i>Moderation: Jagiellonian University</i>
12.00 - 13.30	Transfer to Zabłocie and Lunch Venue: ul. Zabłocie 20/22, Department of Innovation and Entrepreneurship of Municipality of Krakow
13.30 - 14.00	Welcome and short introduction <i>Anna Okońska-Walkowicz, Plenipotentiary of Mayor of City of Krakow for Senior Policy, Healthy Leader 50 (WHO)</i> Interactive presentation of Integer project and partners <i>Toni Caro, I2cat Senior Researcher-DST Unit i2CAT</i>

14.00 - 16.30	<p>How to be supported as a social innovator in Małopolska?</p> <p>Case study 1 – Merkury – a simulator of modern self-service kiosks (Bartosz Kosiński, Mirek Bohatkiewicz)</p> <p>Case study 2 – QR codes QR to help seniors (Marta Salawa)</p> <p>Workshop session #1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of <u>best practices and lessons learnt</u> • Identifying <u>common challenges and barriers</u> for integration of social innovators • Connecting people to <u>cross the silos models</u> • Looking for joint synergies in 4H <p><i>Moderation: Jagiellonian University & Krakow Technology Park</i></p>
16.15 - 16.30	Closing and reflection
19.00	Dinner

<p>29 March 2023</p> <p>VENUE: Life Science Kraków Venue: 14 Bobrzyńskiego Street, meeting point at the reception, main entrance</p>	
9.00 – 9.15	<p>Towards wellbeing and health – best practices from Life Science Kraków</p> <p><i>Kazimierz Murzyn, Director Life Science Kraków</i></p>
9.15 - 10.00	<p>Engaging and empowering stakeholders</p> <p>Case study 1 – Maria Wojtacha, Internationaler Bund Polska</p> <p>Case study 2 – Arkadiusz Tomasiak, Spółdzielnia Socjalna Albert</p> <p>Case study 3 – Wojciech Przybylski, Parenting Technologies</p> <p>Case study 4 – Tomasz Mikosz, FindAir</p> <p>Case study 5 – Karolina Gubała, ARCHEZJA, Fundacja Wspomagająca Wychowanie</p>
Coffee, Tea, Water - during a meeting will be served	
10.00 - 11.30	<p>Workshop session #2:</p> <p>Identification of activities, needs and bottlenecks and their analysis in the field of health, wellbeing and senior policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main quadruple helix collaborations initiatives • Minimum Viable Products and Services for market and society • Existing mechanisms for merging social-driven and business-driven innovations • Identification of opportunities and barriers • How can INTEGER support regional innovators ecosystem <p><i>Moderation: Krakow Technology Park</i></p>
11.30 – 12.00	Sum Up – reflections and recommendations
12.00	Lunch
12.30	Departure to Krakow Balice Airport

Krakow and Malopolska Region Stakeholder Map

On the first day of study visit, on 28th March it is planned to give general introduction to ageing policy in the City of Krakow and Malopolska ecosystem of startups and innovators as a drive for boosting social innovation. The role of research institutions and universities represented by Jagiellonian University and its centre for technology transfer technology is to be demonstrated during the morning session. The social needs and challenges as well as best practices developed and implemented in Krakow and Malopolska will be presented and widely discussed. The afternoon session is planned for an active workshop focused on identification of best practices and identifying common challenges and barriers for integration of social innovators with social activists and innovators on one side, and the technology providers on the other side.

The second day of study visit (29th March) is to give a deep dive into the ecosystem of wellbeing and health oriented initiatives and businesses. The idea is to look for mechanisms of engaging and empowering social and technology driven business innovators to shape the bridge for fruitful collaboration. This translates the capability of KPT and UJ to effectively facilitate the dialogue with regional, national governments and on the EU level to deliver results in terms of creating models of social, digital and business initiatives.

The intention of the workshop is to bring together for the joint workshop participants representing 4H organisations, taking into consideration the variety of their activities and ecosystems they belong to. The stakeholders represent both social innovators, technology driven and digital innovators, but also public institutions, clusters, business support organisations and NGO's. Thanks to participation in the workshop project partners representing two other local/regional innovation ecosystems from Catalonia in Spain and Hamburg region in Germany it will be possible to establish a vibrant platform of sharing know-how, best practices and lessons learnt on implementation on social innovation supported by digital and business innovators.

Key stakeholder selection

The criteria of selection were:

- experience, involvement, knowledge/awareness, in social innovation related to health, ageing, wellbeing;
- motivation to share / collaborate to participate in the definition of joint challenges with other regions; and
- represents the 4 helix.

Contact Information (main stakeholders):

Centre for Evaluation and Analysis of Public Policies	www.ceapp.uj.edu.pl
Krakow Technology Park	https://www.kpt.krakow.pl/en/
Centre for Technology Transfer CITTRU Jagiellonian University	https://www.sciencemarket.pl/
The Regional Centre for Social Policy in Cracow	https://rops.krakow.pl/en
Stowarzyszenie Edukacji Pozaformalnej Meritum	https://www.facebook.com/sep.meritum
Fundacja Internationaler Bund Polska	https://ib-polska.pl/
City of Cracow (Senior Policy)	
Municipal Social Welfare Center	http://mops.krakow.pl/
Wydział Ds. Przedsiębiorczości i Innowacji	
Klaster LifeScience Kraków	https://lifescience.pl/
Foundation in Support of Local Democracy (FSLD)	https://mistia.org.pl/
Parenting Technologies	https://www.linkedin.com/in/wojciech-przybylski-07055982/?originalSubdomain=pl
ARCHEZJA - Fundacja Wspomagająca Wychowanie	
ThessAHALL	https://www.auth.gr/en/
Spółdzielnia Socjalna Albert	https://spoldzielniaalbert.pl/
FindAir	https://findair.pl/

Canvas methodology Day 1

On the first day of study visit there will be both presentations and co-creation workshops. The experts' and stakeholders presentations will focus on showing the examples of ecosystem partners in the Małopolska region (including experience from Jagiellonian University, City of Krakow, local government and social innovators).

The workshop (with in total about 25 persons) will be a moderated discussion. The participants will work in smaller groups, and there will be a forum summary after each round. The summaries will be recorded for later preparation of the summaries.

The main issues to be discussed during workshops will be:

- Identification of best practices and lessons learnt
- Identifying common challenges and barriers for integration of social innovators
- Connecting people to cross the silos models
- Looking for joint synergies in 4H

Canvas methodology Day 2

The co creation session on day2 (29th March) has to be focused on how social driven and business driven innovations can work together (identifying good examples), investigating what are the key obstacles in this field, and finding ways how Integer could act as a gate opener for this collaboration. The key questions to be asked during the session are:

- Name existing mechanisms/instruments/tools for connecting social-driven and business-driven innovations
- What quadruple helix collaborations initiatives worth recommendation do you identify in Krakow/Malopolska?
- Do you know any Minimum Viable Products and/or Services for market and society? within social innovation?
- What are the main challenges for quadruple helix collaborations in Krakow? What is missing?
- How can INTEGER and other similar projects support the regional innovators ecosystem?

Integer study visit Krakow 28-29 March 2023
Co-creation session 2

<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Name existing <u>mechanisms/instruments/tools</u> for connecting social-driven and business-driven innovations	
What <u>quadruple helix collaborations</u> initiatives worth recommendation do you identify in Krakow/ <u>Malopolska</u> ?	Do you know any <u>Minimum Viable Products and/or Services</u> for market and society? within the social innovation?
What are the main <u>challenges for quadruple helix collaborations</u> in Krakow?	
How can <u>INTEGER</u> and other similar projects support regional innovators ecosystem?	

1.4 Hamburg region Study Visit

The Hamburg study visit was structured in a way to find key stakeholders that could help to promote the project activities in the future and to give a good overview on existing activities in the region.

Social entrepreneur strategy city of Hamburg:

- In charge: Hamburg Ministry for Economics and Innovation
- Senate decision from January 2023
- More than 350 partners, ministries, science, welfare, civil society

A key approach at the Hamburg regional study visit was to find ‘multiplying agents’ in the region. A short overview why the different stakeholders were selected:

Cluster Agency GWHH GmbH [3]

The GWHH is a cluster agency owned by Hamburg's Commerce Chamber and the Ministry of Social affairs. It is an important promoter in the healthcare sector with a network of about 3.000 members. The activities are focused on digitisation in the health sector, workforce, supporting start ups and knowledge exchange between different sectors related to healthcare.

Mein Lido [4]

Mein Lido is a good example of how civil society can support innovation in health care. The Max und Ingeburg Herz Foundation supported the start-up company Mein Lido that developed an App that allows people to connect with each other in their own districts to support an independent living.

Working Group Sustainable City Health [5]

The working group is an already existing 4helic cooperation in the Hamburg region led by the civil society organisation Patriotische Gesellschaft. Stakeholders from the public administration, scientific, companies and the civil society are working on sustainability for better health in the Hamburg region.

Optimedis [6]

The company developed a business model on how health systems can be organised in a more healthy and preventive way. It is working in different German and European regions with different systematic approaches and as well in several European innovation projects.

University Hospital Hamburg-Eppendorf (UKE) [7]

The UKE is one of the most important innovators in the healthcare sector in Hamburg. Innovation happens in different fields. In the study visit some examples were chosen, with the focus on collaboration and innovation. Here it was planned to find out about different networks like the national autopsy network (NATON) [8] initiated by the institute for legal medicine [9], or the collaborations of the Institute for Infection Research and Vaccine Development (IIRVD) [10]. Moreover it should be possible to directly find out about the innovation collaboration of the UKE within a presentation of the 3D printing of medicines project [11].

Health Harbour Hamburg / Philips [12]

Philips Dach founded the Health harbour Hamburg. The global player Philips gets in collaboration with local start-up companies, supports them with a special program and opens Philips infrastructure for these companies. This is an interesting approach on how global players and local start-ups can cooperate.

AGENDA

March 30th, 2023 VENUE: Ministry of Social Affairs: Hamburger Street. 37,	
08.45 – 9.00	Reception in the conference rooms in the Ministry
9.00 - 09.10	Opening speech by Kai Schnackenberg

09.10 – 11.50	<p>Presentations Key Stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cluster Agency GWHH ● Senior App Mein Lido (foundation) ● Optimedis ● Working Group Sustainable City Health (4helix)
13.30 – 16.30	<p>University Hospital Hamburg-Eppendorf (UKE) visit</p> <p><i>Including</i></p> <p>13:30 - 13:45 - meeting and welcome</p> <p>until 14:00 - travel time</p> <p>14:00 - 14:20 - forensic medicine / Project NATON (a subproject in NUM)</p> <p>until 14:30 - travel time</p> <p>14:30 - 15:00 - Deanery / Viewing Campus Research II (incl. welcome by the Dean)</p> <p>until 15:15 - travel time</p> <p>16:00 - 16:30 - IIRVD / Visit to the "Institute for Infection Research and Vaccine Development"</p>
March 31st, 2023	
10.00 – 11.30	Health Innovation Port / Philips Company

In the preparation phase of the workshops, it was important for the stakeholder group to develop a common understanding of the project goals. The identification of the partners expectations were very important to organise the study visit in a way that motivates stakeholders to participate.

The presenting stakeholders took much time in discussing what could be interesting to show to the partners from other regions and they took a huge effort to present their activities in an interesting way.

2 CONCLUSIONS

The plan for the three inter-regional study visits foresee networking, collaborative, learning and exchanging actions at three different levels: local/regional, inter-regional and EU wider level.

Furthermore, the main important objectives are:

1. To identify complementarities and common interests between the INTEGER partner organisations;
2. To unveil if there exist effective mechanisms with capacity or potential to merge Social-driven and business-driven innovations to close the gap (e.g. avoid the existing fragmentation and parallel developments build bi-directional bridges between social-driven and business-driven innovations);
3. To identify with stakeholders from the quadruple helix and the three regions the perceived opportunities and barriers towards enhancing more robust 4 helix collaborations (e.g. mind the gap between the knowledge triangle actors and civil engagement; promoting professionals and social entrepreneurs and social actors and citizens to be active part of the regional innovation agenda and funding mechanisms);
4. To uncover how INTEGER can support the different actors, regions and expected outcomes of the call.

REFERENCES

- [1] Col-laboratori Catalunya initiative, <https://colabscatalunya.cat/> [last access 12.04.23]
- [2] Leading Systemic Transformations for the Common Good, www.eohforgood.com [last access 12.04.23]
- [3] Website Gesundheitswirtschaft Hamburg, <https://www.gwhh.de/english/> [last access 12.04.23]
- [4] Website Mein Lido, <https://www.meinlido.de/> [last access 12.04.23]
- [5] Website Patriotische Gesellschaften Hamburg, <https://www.patriotische-gesellschaft.de/de/ueber-uns/arbeitskreise-und-projektgruppen/arbeitskreis-nachhaltige-stadtgesundheit.html> [last access 12.04.23]
- [6] Website Optimedis, <https://optimedis.com/> [last access 12.04.23]
- [7] Website UKE, <https://www.uke.de/english/index.html> [last access 12.04.23]
- [8] Website NATON network, <https://naton.network/en/> [last access 12.04.23]
- [9] Website UKE – Institute for Legal Medicine <https://www.uke.de/english/departments-institutes/institutes/legal-medicine/index.html> [last access 12.04.23]
- [10] Website UKE - IRVD, <https://www.uke.de/english/departments-institutes/institutes/infection-research-and-vaccine-development/index.html> [last access 13.04.23]
- [11] Website UKE – 3D Printing of Drugs, <https://www.uke.de/english/organizational-structure/central-areas/pharmacy/3d-printing-of-drugs/index.html> [last access 13.04.23]
- [12] Website Health Innovation Port, <https://www.healthinnovationport.de/> [last access 13.04.23]